

EASA and FAA Research Findings and Actions—Cabin Air Quality

Susan Michaelis

University of Stirling, Stirling, UK

KEYWORDS

cabin air, environmental control system, oil contamination, fume event

ABBREVIATIONS

APU	Auxiliary power unit
CAQ	Cabin air quality
EASA	European Aviation Safety Agency
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
GCAQE	Global Cabin Air Quality Executive
OPC	Organophosphate compounds
TCAC	Technical cabin air contaminations
TCP	Tricresyl phosphate

ABSTRACT

A brief summary of the historical and recent initiatives undertaken by two of the key aviation regulators, EASA and the FAA is outlined below. This will put into context their roles in the ongoing international aircraft cabin air quality issue.

INTRODUCTION

The Global Cabin Air Quality Executive (GCAQE) presented the historical and current key actions undertaken by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) in relation to aircraft air supplies contaminated by engine-generated compounds via the aircraft bleed air system.

The GCAQE undertook this initiative as EASA, the European aviation regulator had agreed to present their most recent research, but after agreeing to participate, EASA withdrew from both attending and presenting at the conference at short notice. The FAA, the US aviation regulator was asked to present their activities on the cabin air quality (CAQ) topic in February 2017,

but advised they were too busy to find a speaker or to attend.

FAA

In 1994 the FAA provided evidence to the US Senate hearings on airliner CAQ advising that “*all of the studies confirm to us that the air quality aboard an aircraft is at least as good as that commonly found in many other indoor workplaces or office environments.*”¹ The committee reported that “*despite findings of various studies that airliner cabin air is generally safe for healthy people*”, concerns continued to be voiced by flight attendants and passengers.¹

A 2001 review of cabin air quality undertaken by the US National Research Council (NRC) found that oil, hydraulic fluids and their decomposition products posed a moderate concern.² Recommendations included for the FAA to rigorously demonstrate the adequacy of the Federal Aviation Regulations (FARs) related to CAQ and for it to revise standards to protect the health and comfort of crew and passengers if required. The FAA was recommended to investigate and publicly report on the need for and feasibility of installing air-cleaning equipment for removing particles and vapors from the air supplied by the environmental control system (ECS) on all aircraft to prevent or minimize the introduction of contaminants into the passenger cabin during both normal operation and during air quality incidents. Additionally the FAA was recommended to require carbon monoxide (CO) monitor in the supply air ducts and to establish procedures for responding to elevated CO levels. It was also recommended that the FAA collect data related to health and air quality incidents to determine if a relationship existed between health effects or complaints and CAQ.

The 2002 FAA response to the NRC was extensive and advised that “*FAA rulemaking may not have kept pace with public expectation and concern about air quality and does not afford explicit protection from particulate matter and other chemical and biological hazards.*”³ The FAA reported that it would establish an Aviation Rulemaking Advisory Committee (ARAC) to review the existing

standards related to the CAQ and if found inadequate they would propose revisions and/ or new standards. The assessment was to be fairly extensive, suggesting the air quality regulations may evolve into a more comprehensive standard that adopts applicable parts of an existing consensus standard for environmental health. None of the NRC recommendations were met and the ARAC committee was never established and was postponed indefinitely.⁴

In 2003 US public law 108-176 directed the FAA to undertake studies recommended by the NRC related to ozone, pesticides, analysis for contamination of air supply duct filters and the establishment of a reporting system.⁵ The FAA Center of Excellence was established in 2003 with funding through to 2013. This involved numerous studies undertaken by the Airliner Cabin Environment Research (ACER) group, which became Research in Intermodal Transport (RITE) and the Occupational Health Research Consortium in Aviation (OHRCA). The ACER-RITE/OHRCA funded studies from 2003 to 2013 included in excess of \$23 million in FAA grants and \$28 million in matched industry funding. The studies included areas such as recirculation filters; incident monitoring and reporting; medical protocol for bleed air contamination; cabin flow dynamic models and sensors; contaminant transport in aircraft; sensors and prognostics to mitigate bleed air contamination; on-board monitoring and measurement methods; effect of partial pressures on passengers, ozone and flame retardants. In relation to the study addressing exposures to oil fumes and reported ill health, the FAA funded the work but failed to compel airlines to participate, so no definitive conclusions could be drawn.⁴

In 2004, the FAA published an airworthiness directive (AD) involving inspection and cleaning practices on the BAe 146 series aircraft. The AD was reported as *“necessary to prevent impairment of the operational skills and abilities of the flightcrew caused by the inhalation of agents released from oil or oil breakdown products, which could result in reduced controllability of the airplane.”*⁶

A joint NASA/FAA and USAF VIPR (Vehicle Integrated Propulsion Research) project was established in 2011 and consisted of three parts, some of which related directly to aircraft bleed air contamination. For example Jones *et al.* reported that oil contamination in the compressor will result in a fog of very fine droplets (10-150 nm) in the bleed air *“under most operating conditions.”*⁷ It was therefore suggested that *“the development of sensors for detecting oil contamination in aircraft bleed air should focus on ultrafine particle detection and sensing of low contamination levels may require sensitivity to extreme ultrafine particles 10 nanometers and smaller.”*⁷

In 2012 the FAA modernization Reform Act, H.R 658 legislated a study of bleed air quality in aircraft cabins and research and development for cleaning and monitoring technologies for the engine and auxiliary power unit (APU) generated bleed air.⁸ This additionally involved identifying oil based and hydraulic and other toxins in the bleed air supply, to determine the specific amount and duration of toxic fumes in the cabin air that constitutes a health risk to passengers, develop a systematic reporting standard for smoke and fumes events in aircraft cabins and to identify potential health risks to individuals exposed to toxic fumes during flight. The FAA was to require domestic air carriers to allow monitoring of the air in a way that imposes no significant costs on the carrier and does not interfere with the normal operation of the aircraft. The FAA responded to Congress in 2013 as directed.⁹ The required activities were rejected by the FAA as it considered the work was already undertaken or not required. The FAA advised cabin air contamination events were too infrequent, the potential toxicity was speculative and that common standards for cabin air contaminants were lacking, thus inhibiting advanced cleaning and detection technologies. The FAA reported it would *“continue to consider cabin safety risk and sponsor research in this area appropriate to the risk level.”*⁹

The US Congress passed a further law under the FAA Reauthorization Act of 2018.¹⁰ This included making educational materials available via the FAA website

for pilots, flight attendants and maintenance workers on how to respond and report smoke and fume incidents onboard aircraft. The FAA was also directed to undertake research to develop techniques to monitor the bleed air under ACER, including: identifying and measuring the constituents and levels from bleed air events; assessing potential health effects of such constituents on passengers and air crew; identifying air supply monitoring and warning systems for bleed air contamination and potential techniques to prevent fume events. The FAA was required to report back to Congress not later than 18 months on the feasibility, efficacy, and cost-effectiveness of certification and installation of systems to evaluate bleed air quality.

Additionally, in 2018, the FAA issued a Safety Alert for Operators (SAFO).¹¹ The SAFO was issued *“to identify a need to enhance flight crew procedures that mitigate the risk to passengers and crew in the event of odors, smoke and/or fumes.”*¹¹

EASA

In 2009 EASA issued an Advanced Notice of Proposed Amendment (A-NPA) relating to *“Cabin Air Quality Onboard Large Aeroplanes.”*¹² This was to encourage discussion around sources of CAQ degradation. The primary issue of concern was listed as smoke/fume events in the cockpit and /or cabin of which it was stated: *“the vast majority of these events are associated with an abnormal leakage of engine or APU lubrication fluid (aviation engine oil).”*¹²

A Comment Response Document (CRD) to the A-NPA was issued in 2011.¹³ It stated that there was no safety case justifying an immediate and general rulemaking action because:

- There were no accidents (injuries / loss of life / major aircraft damage) with cabin air contamination as root cause;
- Serious incidents involving impairment or incapacitation of crew were rare. A focus was placed on *“dense visible fumes or concentrations of toxic products sufficient to incapacitate crew/passengers.”*

In such cases it was considered that existing procedures and equipment, including oxygen masks, were sufficient to mitigate any potential safety risk;

- The minor *‘nuisance’* of temporary bad smell events—due inappropriate maintenance or mechanical failures—were acknowledged as under-reported and not considered a threat to aviation safety. The frequency was unknown, but suggested to be less common than one in 10,000 flights.

The CRD also stated that a causal relationship between reported health effects and oil / hydraulic fluid contamination was not yet established. Therefore, with no conclusive scientific evidence available the Agency was unable to justify a rulemaking task to change existing designs or certification specifications. EASA advised health effects were not within its primary scope. However, it would continue to monitor the topic and put forward recommendations to further improve the knowledge in the fields of toxicity and health impact of oil fumes and bleed air filter and monitoring technologies.

The final decision in 2012 terminated the rulemaking task 25.035 *‘Cabin air quality on board Large Aeroplanes’* without amending EASA regulations, based on the reasons outlined in the CRD above.¹⁴

In 2014 EASA launched two research projects that were published in 2017. The first of the two projects related to a *“Research Project : CAQ Preliminary Cabin Air Quality Measurement Campaign.”*¹⁵ Sixty-nine measurement flights were performed on eight types of aircraft. Sixty-one of the flights were on bleed air aircraft, with eight undertaken on the bleed free Boeing B787 Dreamliner. Samples were taken at defined flight phases (taxi-out, take off and climb, descent and landing, complete flight). The findings included that traces of meta and para tricresyl phosphate (TCP) isomers and other organophosphate compounds (OPC) were found in most samples. The observed frequency, pattern and concentration levels were similar to findings of other indoor environments. Two types of TCP contamination were defined in two ways:

A) Ubiquitous permanent TCP release

Ubiquitous background low-level TCP can be found in all aircraft types including the B787. The source of this permanent release of TCP was suggested to be textiles, floorings, circuit boards, plastics and outside air, with the levels found said to be similar to other indoor environment and not at levels associated with harm.

B) TCP sourced to oil contamination of aircraft bleed air

1. Non-permanent event triggered TCP /engine oil release into the cabin— Technical Cabin Air Contamination-events (TCAC): 67% of the (500+) samples identified that the TCP contamination occurred sporadically during taxi out, takeoff and climb, descent and landing. These were sourced to oil triggered events in bleed air aircraft and identified as:
 - Primary TCAC-event. These TCP releases were sourced to seal failures and oil overfill and were said to be very rare.
 - Secondary T-CAC events. These TCP levels were sourced to TCP deposits in the bleed air system and air supply ducting related to the permanent low-level oil leakage from the APUs and engines (primary sources). The secondary event TCP release was said to be responsible for the more frequent smell events with non-toxic odourous compounds released into the cabin, of which the frequency was unknown. Inspection of the engines after an event will lead to no findings and the events can be triggered by thermo-mechanical influences on the deposits or the introduction of solvents such as water or deicing fluids.
2. Permanent engine oil /TCP (contaminant) release into the cabin— This type of contaminant release relates to event free scenarios with creeping oil component deposits sourced to bleed air. There is a permanent low-level TCP/oil entry via the bleed

air supply due to chronic seal failure. “Most engines might have a certain turbine oil leak rate”, but this was not identified in this study with the techniques utilized, either with the TCP not reaching the cabin or reaching the cabin but at levels below the limits of detection for the technology utilised. Future testing technology was not noted as requiring improvement and the TCP levels were said to be too low to effect CAQ.

In conclusion the study found:

- The ubiquitous low-level TCP leakage can be differentiated from oil triggered events (Technical cockpit/cabin air contamination);
- Ubiquitous low-level TCP can be from other sources including outside air;
- Permanent low-level TCP can be from the oil / bleed air system;
- Technical cabin air contaminations (TCAC) events have their origin in the bleed air technology;
- High cabin air exchange rates make the cabin less polluted than homes and offices;
- Most of the reported smell events cannot have technical (oil-related) causes due to their known rareness of occurrence;
- Oil triggered events are too low to cause harm to health - acute or chronic neurological effects. Hyperventilation and other causes are under consideration;
- Medical procedures should only be undertaken once the an exact classification of the CAC-event has been established;
- Cabin air contaminant levels are not likely detectable by currently applied bioanalytical methods;
- “The so-called ‘aerotoxic syndrome’ remains completely incomprehensible.”;
- Risk mitigation procedures should be at a reasonable cost benefit ratio;
- Oil investigations using conventional methods are no longer possible because of low levels of contaminants and rare occurrence rates;
- Future ‘large scale study’ should provide data “to end the misguided discussion on CAQ once and for all.”

In 2015 EASA commenced a “*Research project: AVOIL – Characterisation of the Toxicity of Aviation Turbine Engine Oils After Pyrolysis.*”¹⁶ The study reported that “*If seals within the engine are not performing effectively, oil and possibly thermal degradation products of oil can result in contamination of the bleed air. Besides contaminated bleed air, the ECS itself and the ducts can also be a secondary source of contaminants.*” Over 127 compounds were identified in all the oils and during different simulated flight phases with substantial changes in composition occurring during the lifetime of an oil. Six hundred thirty-four peaks were recorded of which 27% could be matched using the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) library. Other findings include:

- High levels of aldehydes and CO;
- TCP was detected but not TOCP;
- No neuronal effects from neuroactive pyrolysis products were found using 30 minute or 24 hour *in vitro* exposures. Exposures of 48 hours or greater identified that neuronal activity was markedly decreased by the majority of TCP isomers and mixtures. Prolonged exposure to pyrolysis products may aggravate their potential neurotoxicity;
- Human sensitivity variability is largely unknown;
- Effects of chemicals combined with other occupational stressors is largely unknown;
- Some of the symptoms may not be caused by exposure to chemicals due to the wide variety and lack of specificity of symptoms reported;
- Conditions in cabin air may differ from the standard conditions on which exposure limits are normally based;
- Future research should focus on neuronal effects of prolonged and repeated exposures, toxicology of chemical substances identified (exposure levels, dose, molecular targets, no effect concentrations); use of exposure limits; effects relating to mixture toxicology; review of symptoms in air crew to investigate if a syndrome can be defined.

EASA suggests that based upon its two previous and other studies, all measurements on board aircraft during

normal operating conditions have shown that the cabin and cockpit air is very good compared to other indoor environments. While according to EASA, no causal association has been identified between cabin air contamination by oil mists and ill health, some incidents had shown a temporal relationship and therefore “*an association was nevertheless plausible and worth of further investigation.*”¹⁷

Therefore in 2017 EASA and the European Commission launched a further larger scale \$2 million study to focus primarily on oil contamination. “*The general objective of this research study is to enable step-advances in the investigation on the quality of the air on board commercially operated large transport aeroplanes and its potential adverse consequences on crew/passenger health in light of the relevant European legislation on quality of indoor air and professional exposure limits.*”¹⁷ The comprehensive strategy outlined under this EU FACTS cabin air quality study, covers both inflight, ground and laboratory testing, chemical analysis, neurotoxicity assessment, biomarkers, risk assessment and countermeasures and mitigation.¹⁸ The FACTS study will primarily focus on oil contamination incidents, i.e. abnormal events and exposure to low-dose mixtures.

DISCUSSION

While cabin air contamination by engine oils and other fluids has a long history, the regulatory approach has been unnecessarily delayed via the above actions. Much of the research has not yielded mitigating actions and protection for human health and flight safety. Importantly, major concerns have been raised about the recent EASA studies and the current FACTS study scope.¹⁹ The concerns addressed the tender process, industry stakeholder input, independence of study and oversight participants and the main aims and methodology of the research. The primary concerns are that the study fails to address chronic low-level exposure to the mixture, the reliance on occupational and indoor air quality guidelines and failure to take into account the current independent science.²⁰

CONCLUSIONS

The FAA and EASA have failed to ensure air quality in aircraft is clean as required by the regulations. The inactions or actions taken have ignored independent science, delayed or negated the implementation of mitigation strategies and have failed to take a precautionary approach.

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